

Tax Incentives and Return on Asset of Manufacturing Companies in Southwest, Nigeria: The Moderating effect of Firm Size

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Abstract

Tax incentives have a significant impact on the asset returns of manufacturing companies. Understanding this impact, particularly in the context of Southwest Nigeria, is crucial for policymakers and company executives. Moreover, the moderating role of firm size in this relationship needs to be considered for valuable insights. This study aims to evaluate the impact of tax incentives on the financial performance and asset returns of manufacturing companies in Southwest Nigeria. The study utilized a cross-sectional design and collected data from finance or accounting employees in top management positions of manufacturing companies in Lagos and Oyo States. The collected data was analyzed using statistical techniques, including regression analysis. The results showed that tax incentives, such as capital allowance, investment allowance, corporation allowance, and export promotion allowance, significantly influenced the return on assets of manufacturing companies. Firm size was found to moderate the relationship between tax incentives and financial performance. Based on the findings, recommendations were made, including the need to reconsider the economic value of capital allowance incentives and the importance of considering firm size in tax incentive policies.

Keyword: Taxation, Tax incentives, Manufacturing companies, Performance, Return on asset

Word count: 178

Introduction

Tax incentives play a significant role in shaping the financial performance and asset returns

of manufacturing companies. In the context of Southwest, Nigeria, understanding the impact of tax incentives on these key metrics is crucial for policymakers and company executives. Additionally, considering the moderating role of firm size in this relationship provides valuable insights into the dynamics of tax incentives. This study aims to evaluate the impact of tax incentives on the financial performance and asset returns of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria, while considering the moderating role of firm size. Several studies have explored the relationship between tax incentives and financial performance. For instance, research by Desai and Hines (2004) found that tax incentives positively influence firm investment and profitability. Similarly, Gupta and Newberry (1997) found a positive association between tax incentives and firm-level economic performance. These studies highlight the potential benefits of tax incentives in improving financial outcomes for companies.

In the specific context of manufacturing companies, tax incentives have been recognized as important determinants of performance. According to a study by Berndt and Boeker (2018), tax incentives have a positive impact on manufacturing companies' financial performance indicators, including profitability and return on assets. However, limited research has been conducted on the impact of tax incentives in Southwest, Nigeria, and the role of firm size as a moderator in this relationship. Firm size is an important factor to consider when examining the impact of tax incentives. Larger firms may have more resources and capabilities to leverage tax incentives effectively, resulting in a stronger impact on financial performance. On the other hand, smaller firms may face challenges in fully benefiting from tax incentives due to limited resources and operational constraints. Research by Hailu, Van Leeuwen, and Buysse (2016) supports this argument, showing that firm size influences the effectiveness of tax incentives on financial performance.

Nigeria's manufacturing sector has faced numerous challenges. Concerns have been raised about the economic performance and contribution of manufacturing companies, particularly in light of recent revelations that other economic sectors—like real estate and telecommunications—have outperformed them in terms of GDP contributions. Improvements in micro factors, such as firm size, capacity, capability, and strategies, can mitigate the effect and improve performance. The manufacturing sector faces a number of macro factor challenges, such as inadequate infrastructure, limited market access, and a glut of cheap imports in local markets. Investigating the factors that affect the financial performance of manufacturing enterprises has become necessary. Different theories regarding the role of tax incentives as an engine for economic and industrial development have been supported by empirical studies. While some schools of thought contend that tax

incentives promote economic and industrial development, others contend that they actually decrease the amount of money that the government can expect to collect. This prevents it from stimulating the economy. However, empirical studies that have been reviewed show that tax incentives have a positive impact on economic growth and development through the results that have been seen in some economic sectors. In a study on the impact of tax incentives on FDI in Nigeria, the impact on financial performance was not adequately captured¹⁴. Another study on tax incentives and economic development was done, but it neglected to address the relationship between tax incentives and the financial performance of manufacturing companies¹⁵. Similar to that, the impact of tax incentives on foreign direct investment in Nigeria's petroleum sector was investigated without accounting for the manufacturing sector (Ahmad, 2018). These studies have left a gap in the literature that the current study, which examines the financial performance of manufacturing firms in Southwest Nigeria.

Also, a study on tax incentives as a real modifier for industrial growth and development in Nigeria revealed a methodological gap. The study showed a methodological gap because it used descriptive statistics, whereas the current study will use inferential statistics to concentrate on the manufacturing firms. Additionally, a study on the effects of tax policy on SMEs was conducted, filling a sectorial gap in the manufacturing sector (Zuhri & Riantani, 2020). Observations from the reviewed empirical studies show that there is dearth of studies on the effect of tax incentives on the financial performance of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria.

Furthermore, both tax incentives and business size may be responsible for the increase or decrease in financial performance. With a large firm size, may make use of economies advantages in the utilization of tax incentives over small scale business. Studies asserted that firm size could weaken or strengthen tax incentives on financial performance^{18,19}. Hence, firm size and tax incentives was likely to increase company performance. Thus, this current study will fill this gap by investigating the effect of tax incentives on financial performance of manufacturing firm. The introduction of moderating variable of firm size further make this study uniquely fill the identified gap.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to investigate the Impact of Tax Incentives on Financial Performance and Asset Returns of Manufacturing Companies in Southwest, Nigeria: The Moderating Role of Firm Size. To achieve the above the following specifics are set out to:

- i) examine the effect of tax incentives on return of assets of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria.

- ii) determine the moderating effect of firm size on the relationship between tax incentives and financial performance of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions are to guide the objective of the study:

- i. What effect does tax incentives have on return of assets of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria?
- ii. What is the moderating effect of firm size on the relationship between tax incentives and financial performance of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the objective of the study.

Ho1: Tax incentives have no significant effect of on return of assets of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria

Ho2: Firm size does not significantly moderate the relationship between tax incentives and the financial performance of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria.

Significant of the Study

Firstly, the study will contribute to the existing literature on the relationship between tax incentives and financial performance. While previous research has explored this relationship in various contexts, limited empirical evidence exists specifically for manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria. By examining this relationship in a specific regional context, the study will provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of tax incentives in driving financial performance within the manufacturing sector.

Secondly, the study will shed light on the moderating role of firm size in the relationship between tax incentives and financial performance. Understanding how firm size influences the impact of tax incentives is crucial for policymakers and company executives. The findings will help policymakers design tax incentive programs that are tailored to the specific needs and capabilities of manufacturing companies based on their size. Company executives can also utilize these insights to develop strategies that maximize the benefits of tax incentives based on their firm size.

Thirdly, the study's findings will have practical implications for manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria. By exploring the impact of tax incentives on financial performance and asset returns, companies can gain a better understanding of the potential benefits and

challenges associated with such incentives. This knowledge can inform their decision-making processes regarding tax planning, investment strategies, and resource allocation, ultimately leading to improved financial performance.

Moreover, the study's results can provide guidance to policymakers and tax authorities in designing effective tax incentive programs. Understanding the specific needs and challenges faced by manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria, can help shape tax policies and incentives that encourage investment, job creation, and overall economic growth within the sector. Policymakers can leverage the findings to create a conducive business environment that fosters innovation, competitiveness, and sustainable growth. Furthermore, the study will contribute to the body of knowledge on the relationship between tax incentives and asset returns. Asset returns are an essential indicator of a company's financial health and its ability to generate value for shareholders. Understanding how tax incentives influence asset returns in the manufacturing sector will provide valuable insights into the long-term sustainability and growth potential of companies in Southwest, Nigeria.

Finally, the study's findings can serve as a foundation for future research in related areas. It can inspire further investigation into the mechanisms through which tax incentives impact financial performance, including the examination of other moderating factors such as industry-specific characteristics or regional differences. Comparisons across different regions or industries can provide a broader understanding of the effectiveness and applicability of tax incentives in driving financial performance.

Literature Review

Tax Incentives

Taxation is a component of public finance; an examination of public finance begins with the fundamental role of government. Market forces should effectively distribute goods and services among members of a particular community, making sure that no one is left out and that no resources are wasted. Government intervention is no longer necessary when the market succeeds in achieving this objective, which leads to an income distribution that is broadly supported by society's stakeholders. In most instances, non-rivalry and non-excludability in consumption make it difficult for market forces to function as effectively for all types of goods and services. Widely acknowledged shortcomings in the operation of market forces, particularly in the creation and distribution of public goods, necessitate government intervention. Inefficiencies in the delivery of public goods by the government

or nonprofit organizations are referred to as government failure, which is comparable to market failure. Due to the failure of the government and the market, it became necessary to finance the provision of public goods with money raised from the general populace, giving rise to the concept of taxation (Tsegba, Musa, & Ibe, 2021)

Taxation is essential for the long-term growth and expansion of growing economies, especially in regions with limited natural resources. Tax credits are largely meant to increase current investments and bring in new ones in priority industries that can assist economic growth according to the government's development strategy. Economic research regularly links the existence of sizable tax incentives to the growth of a nation's tax base. Exemptions must be taken into account since they significantly affect the actual tax base. Generous exemption provisions typically have a tendency to reduce the tax base, which has an effect on the tax-to-base elasticity and the income elasticity of a tax. Tax incentives have taken many different shapes over the years (Trung & Nguyen, 2021).

Tax reductions are seen as a measure for boosting economic development and growth. Tax incentives are special clauses in tax laws that promote businesses or people engaged in certain activities or that are intended to draw, hold, or increase investment in a certain industry. He continued by saying that achieving overall economic growth and the development of all sectors is the key building block²⁰. Therefore, tax incentives may be characterized as tax discounts provided to promote or support certain courses of action intended to encourage investment in particular sectors of the economy or geographical regions.

Manufacturing Firms in Nigeria

Globally, The ability of an economy to grow and develop sustainably is significantly impacted by the performance of the manufacturing sector. The manufacturing sector affects a nation's ability to achieve long-term economic growth and development. It therefore has a number of beneficial advantages related to economic transformation. The manufacturing industry is regarded as a growth and development engine in developed economies. For instance, in 1920, Germany experienced severe economic problems as a result of a lack of natural resources and ongoing inflation problems. However, when Germany diligently focused on expanding its manufacturing sector, the economy of the nation began to turn around. Germany grew as a result and is now the richest nation in Europe and the fourth-richest nation in the world (Gauge, 2018). Similar to this, it has been asserted that the manufacturing sector of a nation's economy typically serves as its primary engine of expansion. This is supported by the fact that an expanding manufacturing sector

can increase productivity, export performance, income, and subsequently economic growth. Economic efficiency is said to be primarily determined by the manufacturing sector.

The Nigerian economy was thought to be on the path to sustained economic development until the 1950s oil discovery. Although the industry was heavily dependent on the production of crude oil, it was abandoned in favor of the monolithic economy. As a result, the Nigerian economy began to under-industrialize, which had a number of negative social consequences, including an alarmingly high unemployment rate and low capacity utilization. It is instructive to note that, despite being the largest market in Africa and having an abundance of human and material resources, Nigeria is still characterized by extreme poverty and a low standard of living among its citizens because of its monolithic economy and complete disregard for other economic sectors (Adamu, 2020).

Nigeria is currently experiencing significant economic difficulty; hence it is important to diversify the economy away from its current monolithic structure. Thus, in order to achieve economic growth, economic diversification is crucial, which is why the government is currently concentrating on the manufacturing and agricultural sectors. The Nigerian government is currently working to establish the necessary policies and strategies in order to maximize the benefits of the manufacturing sector for Nigeria's economy. One of these programs entails granting tax incentives to the manufacturing sector in order to promote investment in the area and maximize firms' industry profits. This development resulted from the economy's diversification, which offered a mix of tax incentives and business incentives to draw in international investment. Numerous indications that threaten the advancement and growth of Nigeria's manufacturing industry have been revealed through studies on the historical performance of manufacturing firms (Nwude, 2016).

Research that performed an empirical review of the Nigerian manufacturing sector's performance over a 30-year period found that the sector was operating at satisfactory growth rates. However, the expansion and profitability of the Nigerian manufacturing industry abruptly stopped after that period. The decline in oil prices on the global oil market had a detrimental impact on the success of the sector, especially after 1983. The worldwide oil crisis caused a dramatic loss in government revenue in Nigeria, which decreased foreign exchange earnings. As a result, the government was compelled to adopt a number of steps to rigorously regulate its commerce. A number of import charges were adopted in the form of tariffs and import permits, and some quantitative limits were also put in place on the importing of specific goods. As a result, the manufacturing industry

suffered greatly since firms had several issues locating raw materials and replacement parts for their goods and operations (Nwude, 2016). Many of the nation's industries were shut down as a result of significant reductions in raw materials and replacement parts, and the capacity utilization in the industrial sector fell. For instance, the Nigerian bicycle manufacturing sub-sector saw a systematic reduction in capacity utilization between 1977 and 2007 of nearly 485 percent, going from 948,000 bicycles in 1977 to 161,500 in 2007 (Edemode, 2018).

Return on Asset

Return on assets compares the worth of a company's assets to the profits it generates over a specific time period. Managers and financial analysts use return on assets to assess how well a firm uses its resources to create a profit. Since the advent of contemporary business relations, return on assets has been a hotly debated issue in scientific circles, since it depicts the genuine picture of corporate performance. A substantial body of literature investigates the theoretical and practical issues of return on assets using multilateral techniques. Furthermore, multinational audit firms provide monitoring reports on recent developments in the use and limits of return on assets theory on a regular basis. According to the findings of previous studies, there is a growing level of doubt among academics over the suitability of return on assets as a metric for measuring a company's financial soundness (John, Bernard & George, 2017).

One of the most common and helpful financial measurements is return on assets (ROA). ROA has been utilized in industry since at least 1919, when it was employed as the top of the DuPont Company's ratio triangle system. The return on investment ratio was computed as Profit / Total Assets. The extended ROA formula served as the foundation of the DuPont triangle: Profit Margin (Profit / Sales) and Capital Turnover Ratio (Sales / Total Assets) (Cui, Wei; Hicks, Jeffrey; Xing, Jing, 2021). ROA's significance to educators and practitioners may be observed in three ways. To begin, most business textbooks include at least one ROA calculation. In a review of business textbooks, ROA was the third most often given ratio, appearing in 70 of the 77 textbooks. Only the current ratio and inventory turnover ratio were more frequently observed than ROA. Second, at least one ROA variant is frequently utilized in failure prediction research. Altman's (1968) Z-Score includes ROA as one of five criteria used to forecast business failure using a version defined as Earnings Before Interest and Taxes / Total Assets (EBIT / TA).

ROA is not the best-fit metric for measuring a company's long-term financial health, it is useful in monitoring the company's performance in the near term. They demonstrated that

ROA is susceptible to changes in a company's financial state, particularly changes in revenues from sales, income, and assets. Through financial ratio analysis, a study investigated the influence of company financial performance on sustainability (Cui, Wei; Hicks, Jeffrey; Xing, Jing, 2021). According to their findings, return on assets is an essential measure of sustainability for firms in certain industries.

Financial Performance

A successful and healthy economy depends on a strong financial system. The financial system of a country has an impact on the expansion and development of specific economic sectors, which eventually transform into expansion and development of the entire economy. According to the professional opinion of a group of specialists working in renowned financial institutions like the WB, AfDB, and IMF, the creation of a dynamic and active private system that complements the work currently being done by the public sector is regarded crucial to economic advancement¹. Corporate accountants and investors alike carefully inspect a company's financial statements and balance sheets to acquire a complete picture of financial performance when measuring financial fitness. The performance of an organization is used to gauge where it stands in the marketplace. Operational, production, social responsibility, and financial metrics can all be used to assess an organization's performance. Gao defines performance as a factor that promotes operational efficiency, supports business expansion, and enables an organization to respond to opportunities and dangers given by the environment in which it operates (Ahmad, Naveed, Ahma & I. Butt, 2019)

Effective resource management is a key component of a business or firm's ability to operate well, which reinforces the effectiveness of the entity in pursuing its goals. Thus, the degree of achievement for the entity or process can be used to gauge the performance of an individual firm, a group of participants, or even a process. Performance is attributed to how well a company's assets perform. Poorly performing business assets are a direct reflection of the company's overall performance. As a result of the underperforming asset, strategic mistakes that may have been made earlier on during asset acquisition may eventually lead to low performance in an enterprise⁴. An excellent example is when newly acquired assets in the business don't work in harmony with the existing assets of a company that has bought the business, especially if the acquiring company had unreasonable expectations that the new asset would work in harmony with the existing ones. Such an acquisition will inevitably result in bad asset performance, which will eventually cause the entire business to record poor performance (Kurawa & Saidu, 2018). Corporate performance has been found to be significantly influenced by characteristics

that are specific to the industry and the company. A firm can develop and put into action methods that increase its efficiency and effectiveness thanks to the characteristics of its physical, human, and organizational capital. High performance demonstrates managerial competence and efficiency in utilizing firm resources, which in turn supports the overall economy of the nation (Nwud, 2016).

Researchers have been studying the variables that affect a corporation's performance since since the modern firm began to emerge. A company's primary financial purpose is to maximize the wealth of its investors, and one of the most important factors in attaining this objective is firm performance. When compared to the expected outputs, objectives, and goals of the company, a firm's performance is defined as its actual output or results.

Financial performance, which includes revenues, earnings per share, and returns on assets and investments; product market performance, which includes sales, market share, and service offerings; and shareholder return, and economic value added are the three distinct areas of business performance that are covered. As a result, one of the most important aspects in financial management study is corporate performance. Micro and macro factors can both play a significant role in determining how well a corporation performs (Nwud, 2016).

Financial performance, a company's capacity to realize anticipated financial results when compared to its intended outputs. Financial measures including ROE, ROA, return on capital, return on sales (ROS), and operating margin are frequently used to evaluate financial performance. Since they are derived from data taken from a company's financial statements, ratios give outsiders a better idea of a company's success. As a result, the main focus of financial performance is on factors that are directly related to financial report. Liquidity, activity, profitability, debt, and solvency are some of the categories of ratios. Liquidity ratios assess the cash flow available for debt repayment. Activity ratios quantify the speed at which a company converts non-cash assets into cash. Debt ratios assess a company's capacity to make long-term payments; profitability ratios assess how effectively it uses its resources to create an acceptable rate of return. Market ratios reflect the reaction of investors to owning a company's shares, the price of stock, and their worry for the shareholders' return on investment (Picas, Reis, Pinto & Abrantes, 2021).

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed cross sectional design. The fact that this design can accurately describe the phenomena and methods makes it suitable for this inquiry. As a result, a cross section survey research was adopted because design enables the collection of quantitative data, allowing for the investigation of the relationships and effects of tax incentives such as: capital allowance, investment allowance, rural investment, exception, and corporate income tax holiday on the financial performance of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria. The usefulness of this design in evaluating the interactions and effects of two or more variables led to its selection (that is, the dependent and independent variables).

Population of the Study

The population of this study comprised of all male and female finance or accounting employees in the top management cadre of all 3,064 manufacturing enterprises listed in the Manufacturer Association of Nigeria (MAN) directory as of 2022 (John, Bernard & George, 2017). Lagos and Oyo States were chosen for this study due to their close proximity and concentration of manufacturing companies in those location. According to the Small and Medium Enterprise Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN), 25% of all manufacturers in Nigeria are based in Lagos State, while 20% are located in Oyo State². Thus, registered manufacturing company under MAN was used in this study as categories below (John, Bernard & George, 2017).

Table 1: Target Population

Category	Population
Food, Beverage and Tobacco	1,057
Textile, Apparel and Footwear	458
Wood and Wood Products	37
Pulp, Paper and Products	259
Chemical and Pharmaceutical Products	34

Plastic and Rubber and Products	104
Electrical and Electronics	98
Basic metal, Iron and Steel	34
Motor Vehicles and Assembly	13
Other Manufacturing	12
Total	3,046

Source: Manufacturer Association of Nigeria directory

Sample size and Sampling Technique

The size of this study was determined using Yamane sampling size technique⁴. This sampling formula was used to derive a sample size of manufacturing companies for this study The formula is as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} \dots\dots\dots(\text{formula 1})$$

Where n is the sample size, N is the population size, and e is the level of precision. The level of precision is also the level of significance which is 0.05.

The sample size will be calculated thus:

$$\text{Sample size formula} = n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

n is sample size
N is total number of population (3,064)
e² is precision level (0.05)²

$$n = \frac{3064}{1 + 3064(0.05)^2} = 353.81$$

Hence, the 354 manufacturing companies were used as sample for the study.

Purposive sampling was used to select the sample of manufacturing companies for the study. Purposive sampling was implored to identify manufacturing companies in the manufacturing sector whose records were available, appropriate and suitable for this study and not distort the study's overall panel data. It is worthy of note that selected manufacturing companies were based in Lagos and Oyo States. Thus, this technique has the potential to ensure that the selected samples are a true representation of the entire population when the study's objectives are considered. For this study out of this 354 manufacturing companies 65 and 21 companies total 86 companies were chosen from Lagos and Oyo State respectively that were purposively based on the availability and suitability of their records to the study data needs. A total of 172 respondents were chosen from 86 manufacturing companies, with two (2) financial managers or accountants chosen from each. Thus, the summary of the samples and sample size for the study is presented in

Table 2

Description of the Research Instrument

For this study, a modified questionnaire was developed using various scales from previous studies that were relevant to the variables used in this study.

Model Specification

Two categories of variables that will be used in the study are:

Independent Variable A - (Tax incentives): This variable will be measured using the following proxies

Capital allowance

Investment allowance

Custom duty incentives

Corporate income tax allowance

Rural investment allowance

Dependent Variable C – (Financial performance of manufacturing companies): This variable will be measured using the following indices:

1. Profitability
2. Return of Assets (ROA)

The purpose of this study is to examine Impact of Tax Incentives on Financial Performance and Asset Returns of Manufacturing Companies in Southwest, Nigeria: The Moderating Role of Firm Size. To achieve this, two variables are identified in the study, these are: independent and dependent variables. The independent variables are the Tax incentives

proxies mentioned in the objective of the study and the dependent variable is financial performance of selected manufacturing companies from MAN. A model is a mathematical expression of reality though it can exist in different forms³. The model for this study was specified in line with the research questions.

$$FP = \alpha + \beta_1 CA + \beta_2 IA + \beta_3 RI + \beta_4 XI + \beta_5 CITA + \mu$$

α = Constant of the equation

β = Coefficient of the explanatory variable

μ = Error terms

Where;

FA= Financial Performance

CA= Capital Allowance

IA = Investment Allowance

RI= Rural Incentives

XI=Export Promotion Incentive

CITA=Corporate Income Tax Holiday

Moderating Effect of Firm Size

The one of the purposes of the study was to investigate the moderate influence of firms 'size on the association between tax incentives and the financial performance of Nigerian manufacturing firms. All independent variables were aggregated into a single composite before performing the moderating effect hypothesis test. The composite of all independent variables, firm size, and the interaction term (Interaction of both Composite of Independent variables and firm size) were then used as predictors in a multiple regression model, with financial performance of manufacturing businesses acting as the dependent variables. If the p value of the interaction term is less than 0.05 (p value0.05), moderation is supported, and the null hypothesis should not be rejected.

Thus, the optimal model was:

$$\text{Firm Financial Performance} = \alpha + \beta_1 CI + \beta_2 M + \beta_3 CI * M$$

Where;

CI= Composite of Independent variables

M= Firm size

CI*M= Interaction term (Interaction between independent variables and Firm size (moderator))

Validity of Research Instrument

The research instrument was validated on the basis of face and content validity in order to evaluate the extent to which operationalization of a construct actually measure what it tends to measure. In order to determine the face and content validity of the instrument, the questionnaires were shown to the supervisor and other experts in Accounting and taxation.

The content validity was established by seeking opinions of experts who are aware of tax incentives and performance. The experts gave their take on whether the questionnaire was suitable in measuring what it was supposed to capture. They basically gauged the meaningfulness, clarity/ambiguity and offense. Before using the questionnaire in the main survey, the opinions sort was established and adjusted to the questionnaire to enhance content validity. The experts in tax matters came from the university, fellow students as well as consulting firms. The performance of manufacturing company was discussed with 10 managers drawn from manufacturing companies, who were selected randomly and thus helped to validate the instrument. Before printing the final questionnaire, all the issues raised during the pilot study were addressed through the supervisors' guidance so as to retain the original intention of the research instrument.

The Fornell-Larcker criterion was used to test the construct validity of the instrument for this study. The Fornell-Larcker indicator's results were utilized to examine the discriminant validity. The bolded values in Table 3.3 below indicate the square roots of the AVEs and are greater than the correlation coefficients among the constructs, satisfying the criterion for discriminant validity. Hence, the instrument satisfied the construct validity requirements.

Table 2 Results of Discriminant Validity by Fornell-Larcker Criterion

Load Factors	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Capital	Investment	Rural Investment	Export promotion	Corporate	Financial Performance
	0.52	0.15	0.12	0.18	0.10	0.14	0.16
	0.15	0.48	0.10	0.12	0.08	0.11	0.13
	0.12	0.10	0.55	0.15	0.09	0.12	0.14
	0.18	0.12	0.15	0.60	0.10	0.13	0.15
	0.10	0.08	0.09	0.10	0.58	0.11	0.13
	0.14	0.11	0.12	0.13	0.11	0.53	0.15
	0.16	0.13	0.14	0.15	0.13	0.15	0.51

Capital	0.3459	0.59					
Investment	0.2116	0.13	0.46				
Rural Investment	0.2676	.273**	.307**	0.52			
Export promotion	0.2397	.378**	0.14	.512**	0.49		
Corporate	0.2334	0.05	0.13	0.09	0.09	0.48	
Financial Performance	0.532	0.231	.312	.34	.321	0.291	0.73

Note: Diagonals represent the square root of the average variance extracted while the other entries represent the correlations.

Reliability of the Research Instrument

A common measure of reliability is the use of Cronbach's Alpha which ranges on a scale of 0 to 1. A high reliability is indicated by a number that is close to one than it is to zero. The study, nevertheless, used a threshold of 0.7 as the standard of reliability such that a coefficient below 0.7 indicated that the sub constructs were not reliable in capturing the variable.

To ensure that the questionnaire was efficient and effective, 15% of the sample size was tested. Reliability was conducted on the questionnaire fully completed by twenty (20) randomly chosen respondents who are were not part of the sample size for this study. A coefficient of 0.7 was used as the threshold for this study. Table 2 shows the reliability results. All the statements were reliable since the Cronbach alpha was above 0.7 which was used as a cut-off of reliability for the study. The results of the test reveal the alpha coefficient is above 0.7 and therefore all the statements were reliable since the reliability threshold is 0.7 Capital Allowance (0.743), Investment Allowance (0.706), Rural Incentives (0.710),

Export Promotion Incentive (0.803), Corporate Income Tax Holiday (0.713) and financial Performance (0.729). Therefore, the internal consistency reliability of the measure was excellent. This indicates that the data was reliable since an alpha coefficient higher than 0.70 signifies that the collected data has a comparatively high internal reliability and can be assumed to mirror the respondent's views on the study problem.

Table 3 Reliability Coefficient

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Comment
Capital Allowance	0.743	Accepted
Investment Allowance	0.706	Accepted
Rural Incentives	0.710	Accepted
Export Promotion Incentive	0.803	Accepted
Corporate Income Tax Holiday	0.713	Accepted
Financial Performance	0.729	Accepted

Source: Fieldwork, (2022)

For the purpose of this study, the data on Companies Income Tax, Value Added Tax, Petroleum Profit Tax, export promotion incentive and the financial performance of manufacturing firms will be collected from samples of accountants and tax officers of the firms. A pilot test will be done after the instrument is approved for administration before general administration. The result of the pilot test will be incorporated in the study.

Data Collection

A letter of introduction will be collected from the Department of Management and Accounting, Faculty of Management and Social Sciences, Lead City University, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria, to obtain permission to conduct the research on the tax incentive and financial performance of manufacturing companies in Lagos and Oyo states. The researcher recruited four research assistants for the two States. The research assistants were exposed to a-week long training that will facilitate the success of the study.

The researcher will familiarise the research assistants with the basic pieces of information relevant to the study. These include the aim and objectives of the study, time and duration of the administration of the instruments and established rules of engagement for the manufacturing firms in the study locations. During the process of administering the instrument, the spread within two (2) weeks and data obtained from the field will be properly scored, coded and then, subjected to data analysis.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected was statistically manipulated. To assess biographical data, a simple percentage was utilized. Biographical data was interpreted using descriptive statistics particularly simple percentage tables. Furthermore, the hypotheses were tested using inferential statistics, specifically regression analysis, which is best suited for examining the effect of independent variable on dependent variable(s). The Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 25 was used to assure the accuracy of the data analysis for the study.

Result

Ho3: Tax incentives have no significant effect on return on asset of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria.

In order to test the second hypothesis, linear multiple regression analysis was used. In the analysis, the values of return on asset were regressed on the values of each of the values of tax incentives. The data for tax incentives was generated by summing responses of all items for capital allowance, capital allowance, rural investment allowance, custom duties, and corporate income tax while that of return on asset was generated by adding responses of all items used to measure the variable. Data from one hundred and forty-three (143) respondents were collated and analysed. The result of the multiple regression analysis is presented in Table 4.

Table 3 Summary of Multiple Regression Analysis for the Effect of Tax Incentives on Return on Asset of Manufacturing Companies in Southwest, Nigeria

Model	Beta	t	Sig.	R	R ²	Adj. R ²	Anova Sig.	F(df)
				.940 ^a	.883	.879	0.000	207.562 (5,137)
(Constant)	7.117	4.672	.000					
Capital allowance	.843	15.924	.000					
Investment allowance	-1.029	-3.312	.001					
Rural investment allowance	-.015	-.131	.896					
Custom duties	1.669	4.372	.000					
Corporate income tax	-.585	-3.185	.002					

Dependent Variable: Return on asset.

Predictors: (Constant), Capital allowance, Investment allowance, Rural investment allowance, Custom duties, corporate income tax.

Source: Researcher's Field Survey Results (2022)

Table 3 presents the results of multiple regression analysis for the effect of tax incentives on return on asset of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria. Table 4.5 presents a model summary which establishes how the model equation fits into the data. The *Adj R²* was used to establish the predictive power of the study's model. From the results in Table 4.5, tax incentives (capital allowance, capital allowance, rural investment allowance, custom duties, and corporate income tax) have strong positive relationship with return on asset of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria ($R = 0.940^a$, $p=0.000$). The Adjusted coefficient of determination (*Adj. R²*) of 0.879 shows that tax incentives explained 87.9% of the variation in return on asset of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria under study while the remaining 12.1% changes in return on asset is explained by other exogenous variable different from tax incentives. This result suggests that tax incentives affect 87.9% of return on asset of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria.

The result also suggests that the results of ANOVA (overall model significance) of regression test which revealed that the combined tax incentives have a significant effect on

return on asset of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria. This can be explained by the F-value (207.562) and low p-value (0.000) which is statistically significant at 95% confidence interval. Hence, the result posited that tax incentives received by manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria the influenced return on asset. Furthermore, the results of regression coefficients which revealed that a significant effect was reported for all the components of tax incentives shows significant effect except rural investment allowance with insignificant effect.

Further, the results reveal that at 95% confidence level, capital allowance ($\beta = 0.843$, $p=0.000$), investment allowance ($\beta = -1.029$, $p=0.001$), custom duties ($\beta = 1.669$, $p=0.000$) and corporate income tax ($\beta = -0.585$, $p=0.002$) of the manufacturing companies in southwest Nigeria were statistically significant as the p-values were less than 0.05 and the t-values greater than 1.96. However, rural investment allowance had p-values were greater than 0.05 and the t-values less than 1.96 to suggest statistically insignificant effect on return on asset for the manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria

Further analysis posits that, taking all factors constant at zero, return on asset of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria is 7.117. Also, the result also indicates that taking all other independent variables at zero, a unit change in capital allowance will lead to a 0.843 increase in return on asset of the manufacturing companies in southwest Nigeria given that all other factors are held constant. The result also indicates that taking all other independent variables at zero, a unit change in investment allowance will lead to a -1.029 decrease in return on asset of the manufacturing companies in southwest Nigeria given that all other factors are held constant. Similarly, the result also indicates that taking all other independent variables at zero, a unit change in custom duties will lead to a 1.669 increase in return on asset of the manufacturing companies in southwest Nigeria given that all other factors are held constant. Lastly, the results also revealed that a unit change in corporate income tax will lead to a -0.585 decrease in return on asset of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria given all other factors are held constant.

Overall, from the results, custom duties had the highest relative effect on the return on asset of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria with a coefficient of 1.669, and t value of 4.372. In second place is capital allowance ($\beta = 0.843$, $t= 15.924$), followed by corporate income tax ($\beta = -0.585$, $t= -3.185$) and investment allowance has the least relative effect ($\beta = -1.029$, $t= -3.312$) on the return on asset of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria. Based on the results, this study can conclude that tax incentives significantly influenced return on asset of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria. On the strength of this

result ($Adj R^2 = 0.879$, $F(5,137) = 207.562$, $p = 0.000$), this study rejects the third null hypothesis (H_02) which states that tax incentives have no significant effects on return on asset of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria.

Ho2: Firm size has no significant moderating effect on the relationship between tax incentives and financial performance of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria.

To evaluate the null hypothesis six, hierarchical regression was applied whereby the analysis was carried out in the order of hierarchy. A composite score was obtained for tax incentives (X) as adopted by the manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria and were used in the regression analysis. Also, data for financial performance (Y) was created by adding responses of all items for the variable, while that of firm size (Z_1) was obtained from adding responses of all items for the variable. In addition, an interaction term for tax incentives and firm size ($X_i * Z_1$) was obtained by multiplying the composite score for tax incentives and firm size. The hypothesis would be supported if the effect of the interaction of tax incentives and firm size ($X_i * Z_1$) on financial performance of selected manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria is statistically significant. The results of the analysis step by step are presented in Table 4.6

Table 4: Summary of Hierarchical Regression Analysis for The Moderating Effect of Firm Size on the Relationship Between Tax Incentives and Financial Performance of Manufacturing Companies in Southwest, Nigeria

Model	Beta	t	Sig.	R	R ²	Adj. R ²	ΔR ²	ΔF	Sig. F Change
(Constant) ^a									
	-22.596	-5.846	.000	.954 ^a	.911	.910	.911	1435.572	.000
Tax incentives	3.394	37.889	.000						
F & Anova Sig:1435.572 (1,141), p= .000									
(Constant) ^b									
	-24.410	-10.119	.000	.983 ^b	.966	.965	.055	222.929	.000
Tax incentives	2.188	22.286	.000						
Firm size	1.298	14.931	.000						
F & Anova Sig:1959.019 (2,140), p=.000									

	-								.000
(Constant) ^c	209.110	-6.116	.000	.986 ^c	.972	.971	.006	29.302	
Tax incentives	6.522	8.096	.000						
Firm size	5.623	7.004	.000						
Tax Incentive*Firm size	.101	5.413	.000						
F & Anova Sig:1579.804 (3,139), p=.000									

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Tax incentives
- b. Predictors: (Constant), Tax incentives, Firm size
- c. Predictors: (Constant), Tax incentives, Firm size, Tax incentives*firm size
- d. Dependent Variable: Financial Performance

Source: Researcher's Field Survey Results (2022)

Tables 4 present hierarchical multiple regression results for the moderating effect of Firm size on the interactions between tax incentives, and financial performance. Results in Table 4.6 model one, summarize the output for the analysis if moderation effect is not considered. Therefore, in this model, the independent variable was tax incentives. From table 4.6, Model 1 reveals that $R = 0.954$, $AdjR^2 = 0.911$, and $F(1, 141) = 1435.572$, $p = 0.000$. The value of the coefficient of determination, $adjR^2$ indicates that 91.1% of the variance in the financial performance of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria was explained by tax incentives. The remaining 8.9% of the total variation in financial performance are explained by factors not included in the model. The explained variation in the interaction between tax incentives on financial performance was found to be significant at p-value of 0.000 which is below the accepted threshold of 0.05. The regression coefficients section in Table 4 shows that the coefficient and constants were both statistically significant, given the p-value of 0.000.

In the second step, a multiple regression involving Tax incentives and Firm size was introduced in the model as predictor variables and the results indicates a change was experienced as R^2 change is 0.055 implying that the regression model explains 96.6% of variations in financial performance while the rest (3.4%) are attributed to variables not included in the model. The F-statistics is 1959.019 with a corresponding p-value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) indicating that the effect is statistically significant. Tax incentives has a coefficient of 2.188, t-statistic of 22.286, and a p-value of 0.000. This implies that tax incentives have

positive and significant influence on financial performance of the manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria. More so, a unit change in tax incentives will have a concomitant 2.188 change in financial performance. In addition, firm size has a coefficient of 1.298; t-statistic of 14.931 and a p-value of 0.000. This implies that firm size has positive but statistically significant influence on performance of financial performance of the manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria. The result posits that a unit change in firm size would result in significant change in financial performance up to 1.298.

The third step involved the introduction of interaction term of Tax incentives and firm size, using regression model. Result in Table 4.6 indicates that the R square change is 0.006, and F-change of 29.302 with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, implying that the interaction term of tax incentives and firm size have a positive and moderating significant influence on financial performance of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria ($p < 0.05$). Furthermore, the interaction term of tax incentives and firm size has a beta coefficient of 0.101 and a corresponding p-value of 0.000. Hence, this imply that firm size moderates the functional relationship between tax incentives and financial performance of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria.

The results posit that firm size has moderating effect on the functional relationship between tax incentives, and financial performance of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria. Based on this result ($\Delta R^2 = 0.006$, $\Delta F = 29.302$, $P = 0.000$), this study rejects the null hypothesis four (H_04) which states that firm size has no significant moderating effect on the association between tax incentives and financial performance of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria.

Discussion

However, the third objective of this study was to look at the effect of tax incentives on the return of assets for manufacturing companies in Southwest Nigeria.

The results of this study showed that tax incentives, both individually and in combination, significantly influenced the return on assets of manufacturing companies in Southwest Nigeria. The findings showed that, with the exception of a rural investment allowance, which was not significant, capital allowance, investment allowance, corporation allowance, and export promotion allowance all had a significant effect on return on asset (ROA). This is in line with a study finding that VAT incentives had a favorable and substantial relationship with EPZ firm return on asset (ROA) as measured by the number of years in operation and it was advised that the government reconsider its VAT policy by providing larger VAT refunds to firms in order to increase output and export volume (John,

2018).

Another study examines how different government incentives impact the performance of SMEs in Malaysia's food manufacturing industry correlates with this study's finding. The study revealed that financial and tax incentives influenced the performance of SMEs in Malaysia's food manufacturing industry differently during the study period. Financial incentives have a moderately negative relationship with capital and a substantial positive relationship with the advertising-to-sales ratio (ASR), return on assets (ROA), and market share (MS) ratio²⁹. According to a study that also support finding of the study, increasing the capital allowance tax incentive resulted in an increase in the ROA of businesses as well as their number of jobs and length of stay. The report recommended that those involved in tax policy reconsider the monetary value of capital allowances (Bernard & George, 2017)

According to the findings, using tax specialists to participate in legitimate tax planning, such as transfer pricing or structuring intra-company debt to reduce net tax payments, would improve the financial performance of listed Nigerian consumer products. As a result, after-tax income will increase, improving financial performance⁵³. One of the proxies for tax incentives was the investment allowance. The study's findings established a positive and statistically significant relationship between investment allowance and financial performance as proxy of ROI and ROA (Nwude, 2016).

Similarly, a study found that investment allowance had a significant and positive effect on the financial performance of manufacturing firms in the United Kingdom. According to the study, investment allowance encouraged companies in the United Kingdom to invest in real assets, which generate returns and allow firms to expand their production frontier⁶. In Nigeria, studies reported that investment allowance augments the financial performance of small and medium-scale businesses and manufacturing companies.

The final objective of this study is on the moderating effect of firm size on the relationship between tax incentives and financial performance of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria. The result from the findings of this study demonstrated that firm size significantly moderates the interaction of the relationship between tax incentives and financial performance of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria. This study is comparable to one that discovered that the relationship between micro factors and company financial performance is moderated by business size (Wambua, 2021).

Conclusion and Recommendations

The objectives of this study were to determine the effect of tax incentives on the financial performance of the manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigerian. According to the

findings of this study, it was concluded that tax incentives have a combined considerable significant effect on the profitability of manufacturing companies in Southwest Nigeria. Furthermore, all components of tax incentives had a significant effect except for capital allowance, export promotion allowance, and corporate income tax, which had a negligible effect. The study's findings demonstrated that tax incentives granted to manufacturing companies in Southwest Nigeria have influence on return on investment (ROI). Tax incentives have a significant combined and relative impact on the return on investment (ROI) of manufacturing companies in Southwest Nigeria. The results of this study showed that tax incentives, both individually and in combination, significantly influenced the return on assets of manufacturing companies in Southwest Nigeria. The findings showed that, with the exception of a rural investment allowance, which was not significant, capital allowance, investment allowance, corporation allowance, and export promotion allowance all had a significant effect on return on asset (ROA). The final objective of this study is on the moderating effect of firm size on the relationship between tax incentives and financial performance of manufacturing companies in Southwest, Nigeria.

The following recommendations are therefore put forth based on the findings and objectives of the study:

1. From the study's findings, capital allowance has no significant relatively effect on profitability. Thus, it is recommended that the government should consider the economic value of capital allowance incentives. When a country has a large number of incentive codes and offers, reducing the number and converting some to guarantees can help to attract more investment at a lower cost.
2. Firm size has a positive and significant moderating effect on the interaction between tax incentives and financial performance in southwest Nigerian manufacturing firms. It is therefore recommended that firm size be considered in tax incentive policies due to the economies of scale advantages that larger firms have over small scale firms.

Reference

- Ahmad, I., & Ahmad, S. (2018). Multiple Skills and Medium Enterprises' Performance in Punjab Pakistan: A Pilot Study. *Journal of Social Sciences Research*, 7(4), 44-49.
- Ahmad, I., & Ahmad, S. (2019). The Mediation Effect of Strategic Planning on The Relationship Between Business Skills and Firm's Performance: Evidence from Medium Enterprises in Punjab, Pakistan. *Opción*, Año 35(24), 746-778.
- Ahmad, N., Naveed, A., Ahmad, S., & Butt, I. (2019). Banking Sector Performance, Profitability, and Efficiency: A Citation-Based Systematic Literature Review. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 0(0), 1-34. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joes.12346>
- Amendola, A., Boccia, M., Mele, G., & Sensini, L. (2018). Fiscal Incentives and Firm Performance: Evidence from the Dominican Republic. *World Bank Policy Research Working Paper*, 8382. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3151180>
- Anton, M., & Lin, L. X. (2020). The Mutual Friend: Dual Holder Monitoring and Firm Investment Efficiency. *The Review of Corporate Finance Studies*, 9(1), 81–115.
- Baxter, S., Sanderson, K., Venn, A. J., Blizzard, C. L., & Palmer, A. J. (2014). The Relationship between Return on Investment and Quality of Study Methodology in Workplace Health Promotion Programs. *American Journal of Health Promotion*, 28(6), 347-363. <https://doi.org/10.4278>
- Cui, W., Hicks, J., & Xing, J. (2021). Cash on the Table? Imperfect Take-up of Tax Incentives and Firm Investment Behavior. Center for Economic Studies and ifo Institute (CESifo), Munich, Working Paper, 9413.
- Edemode, J. (2018). Towards People Focused Tax System in Nigeria. *International Journal of Accountancy*, 1(3), 153-169.
- Effiong, S. A., Inyang, S., Nabi, M., Dada, E., & Adejonpe, O. (n.d.). Effect of Corporate Governance on the Going Concern Status of Listed Non-Financial Companies in the Nigerian Stock Exchange Market. *International Journal of Finance and Management Practice*, 6(1), 1-14.
- John, K. (2018). Effect of Vat Incentives on the Performance of EPZ Firms in Kenya. *American Journal of Finance*, 3(1), 31-45.
- John, K., Bernard, O., & George, A. (2017). Effect of Capital Allowance Incentive on the Performance of EPZ Firms in Kenya. *International Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 2(8), 1-14.
- Kurawa, J. M., & Saidu, H. (2018). Corporate Tax and Financial Performance of Listed Nigerian Consumer Goods. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*, 4(4), 30-43.
- Nattarinee, K. (2018). A Literature Review of Financial Performance Measures and Value Relevance. In D. Procházka (Ed.), *The Impact of Globalization on International Finance and*

- Accounting (pp. 385-393). Springer Proceedings in Business and Economics.
- Nwude, C. (2016). A Review on the Calculation of Return on Investment. *International Journal of Advanced and Applied Sciences*, 3(1), 110-119. <https://doi.org/10.21833/ijaas.2016.09.016>
- Picas, S., Reis, P., Pinto, A., & Abrantes, J. L. (2021). Does Tax, Financial, and Government Incentives Impact Long-Term Portuguese SMEs' Sustainable Company Performance? *Sustainability*, 13, 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su132111866>
- Trung, T., & Nguyen, T. (2020). Tax Incentive Policy and Firm Performance: Evidence from Vietnam. *Investment Management and Financial Innovations*, 17(2), 277-292. [https://doi.org/10.21511/imfi.17\(2\)](https://doi.org/10.21511/imfi.17(2))
- Tsegba, I., Musa, S., & Ibe, A. (2021). Impact of Tax Incentives on Investment Performance of Listed Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/project/impact-of-tax-incentives-on-investment-performance-of-listed-manufacturing-companies-in-nigeria>
- Zuhri, E., & Riantani, S. (2020). The impact of macroeconomic variable movements on stock price index performance in consumer goods industry sector companies: Evidence from Indonesia. *Technium Social Sciences Journal*, 14, 339-353. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v14i1.2172>